

Business Model for Expansion of Electric Vehicles and Sustainable Racing Culture in India

†* Dhruv J. Jani, †Kartik Jindal, ††Sushmit Bafna, †Ujwaldarshan

†School of Mechanical Engineering, VIT Vellore, India

††School of Chemical Engineering, VIT Vellore, India

**Corresponding author: dhruv.jani602@gmail.com*

Abstract

India's aim to increase sustainability for the future, has seen the Government of India's efforts to set six and half million electric vehicles in India by 2020. This implores a gradual shift of the automobile industry from conventional engines to electric vehicles backed by depletion of fossil fuel resources and an environmental mindfulness. These push us to see the immense potential in the Indian electric motorsport market and to support our aim of a greener racing and entertainment experience.

The objective here is to discuss the feasibility of an electric vehicle racing market in India with respect to formula student electric racing teams in India, namely Team Ojas, based in Vellore Institute of Technology (VIT), Vellore. This paper discusses the marketing strategies that can be adapted to sell electric racing cars in Indian market with customer-centric and business-centric approaches. In our efforts to make the electric driving experience accessible to all, we intend to provide our electric race car on majority of the pre-existing race tracks with different plans; rent & drive for immediate payment and racing experience, and subscriptions for monthly payment and racing experience.

Keywords: Rent & Drive, Subscription, Forecast, Formula Student

Introduction

Going back in time to 1886, where the creation of the first motorcar was the biggest breakthrough in the Transport Sector. As time went by and technology advanced the idea of racing cars against each other, Motorsport was introduced and Racing became one of the most popular sports within a short span of time due to the thrill and rush involved.

In recent years, the awareness of a cleaner environment has posed a problem to the combustion engine. The large amount of pollution caused by these engines is astonishing, thus the importance of alternative fuels is coming into picture, heralded by electric vehicles. Their popularity has grown over the years, and the development in technology has just supported their growth. electric vehicles have swept the automobile market and have accomplished various tasks at once: Sustainability of racing, pollution problems, commute of the public.

We aim to bring racing to everyone out there and make it cheap and accessible to each and every part of our society. We want everyone to feel the thrill and excitement that a driver goes through while he is racing. We wish to indulge in the lifestyles of the common man and make it interesting and fun. Not only can we provide the adrenaline on the track but also off it, with our rooftop race track and top-class hospitality with our resto-bars and fine dining restaurants. We will set a landmark in the world, where the world can get an insight of the life of a race car driver. And along with this, there are several benefits of electric cars over conventional combustion engine cars.

Sustainable Production Plan

The assembly line is U shape design. A Just in Time (JIT) method of manufacturing which reduces wastage of time and resources. The main aim of plant is not only to produce a car with zero CO₂ emissions but to also have minimal carbon emissions during the actual production of the car itself, which can be achieved manufacturing of car in a green

factory which incorporates various methods of limiting the use of fossil fuels and maximizes the use of sustainable energy sources like solar power etc.

This leaves us with 2 favourable scenarios in the production of electricity

- 1)The availability of balance electricity produced
- 2)The availability of carbon credits due to being a green factory with very few carbon emissions

The availability of balance electricity enables us to distribute the surplus electricity produced.

Table 1 Sources mentioned alongside the parameter

No. of units generated from Solar Plant of 250 kW capacity [1]	1,75,000
Yearly requirement of Electricity in the plant (no. of units) [2]	60,000
Spare Units	$1,75,000 - 60,000 = 1,15,000$
Setup Cost for Roof Top Solar On Grid Plant [3]	₹65,80,000.00
Avg. cost of sale of a unit generated by solar panel [12]	₹4.25
Revenue generated by selling excess units	$= 4.25 * 1,15,000 = ₹4,88,750.00$

Fig. 1 Designed using SolidWorks

Fig. 2 Source: Twitter Link: <https://pbs.twimg.com/media/DSxdGjGW0AEhNsZ?format=jpg&name=small>

Market Segmentation and Trend Analysis

The target is to make electric racing more accessible to the youth demographic alongside the group of amateur and professional racers. It is also our aim to provide an overall entertainment hub to experience the driver’s lifestyle.

The sale of premium cars (above 25 lakhs) expected to hit 1 lakh units per year by 2020 [4]. India’s switch to electric vehicles will be rapid. 7.3 million electric vehicles are expected to be on roads by 2030 with an increase to 31 million by 2040 [5]. While racing is well-established in Europe or America, in India it is still a new sport. But it is fast gaining popularity especially among young people in urban India. With half of the population under the age of 25 - the potential for growth is huge [6]. F1 became the fastest growing sport brand on social media in 2017, heading the likes of Formula E, the Premier League, NFL and leading sports clothing brands such as Adidas, Puma and Nike. F1’s social media platforms Facebook, Twitter, Instagram and YouTube now boast a total of 11.9 million followers, reflecting an increase of 54.9 percent compared to 2016 [7].

Potential Markets

We have divided the potential markets into three segments mentioned as below:

- Tier 1 and Tier 2 cities- The Human Development Index classifies the cities in India on the following parameters- demographics, infrastructure, finance and economy.
- Electricity cost – It is obviously essential for an electric car to charge their batteries and hence we choose cities with lower electricity cost.
- Current CO₂ emissions in the cities - cities already facing problems from pollution and smog etc. would possess faster growing customer bases and will also help curb the problems of air pollution sooner [8].

Table 4 Source: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rser.2014.12.036>

State	City	Tier	Actual CO2 emission (Gg)
Maharashtra	Mumbai	1	3320.66
Maharashtra	Pune	2	2307.94
Telangana	Hyderabad	1	7788.02
Haryana	Gurugram	2	2124.43
Delhi	Delhi	1	10867.51
West Bengal	Kolkata	1	1886.60
Karnataka	Bengaluru	1	8608.00
Tamil Nadu	Chennai	1	4180.28
Tamil Nadu	Coimbatore	2	3091.67
Chandigarh	Chandigarh	2	1983.87
Gujarat	Ahmedabad	2	2273.72
Gujarat	Surat	2	1983.87

Customer Segmentation

- On the basis of Rent and Drive Karting: We want to reach out to all sections of society and make Electric Racing accessible to on and all. With this effort we would like to bring the karting experience to all sections and age groups of the world.
 - School Students: People who want to entrain on a journey of adventure and experience the feeling of fast vehicles, along with their schoolmates. These are a small part of the innovators section present in the society. Competitions like Emirates School Karting Championship are just motivating more school pupils to go karting, where teams of 3-4 people collaborate in a team of people aged 7-18 to utilize Team Skills [8].

- College Students: People who are amused by danger and fast speeds along with trying out new things while in college. These people want to experience life to its fullest and are not afraid of taking up new challenges. They are the large part of the innovators section present in the society.
- Adults: It is that section of society which consists of the people who always want new experiences from their life. They want to make their lives happening and exciting all the time and would love to experience a new version of karting with their friends. They require a day out from their hectic lives and this is one of the best concepts that they can experience with their colleagues.
- On the basis of Go-Karting and Weekend Racing Industry: We wish to target the most popular race tracks to give our product the maximum reach possible to our potential customers. We want to give our customers a driving pleasure that they have never experienced before.
 - Amateur/Weekend Racers: People who are regular racing enthusiasts come to race tracks and test their skills. These racers want to have a fun-filled experience and experience the best performance from their go karts. These people deserve good karts to develop their skills and enhance them to take them to the next level of motorsport racing [15].
 - Professional Racers: People who race day-in day-out and have excellent skills in racing deserve the best performance from their karts. To excel in competitions and beat their competitors so that they could get their team to the top of the leaderboard, they need top of the class technology to support them to their victories. These racers can opt for the Platinum package where they have all the benefits of the Elite package and also special care for fellow racers [15].
- On the basis of potential customers at Ojas World: We would like to give a total entertainment package to our customers that visit us over at The Ojas World. We wish that our customers will have the most entertaining experiences of karting while visiting The Ojas World.
 - Young Active Generation: This section of society is the most enthusiastic and adrenaline rushed people in the world. They seek for adventure all the time and are ever ready to try out new things. With expenses of people on leisure activities on the rise, 8% of their total expenditure of 12 trillion dollars by 2020, will be on leisure [9]. They are the innovators for the subscription scheme present on every large platform with up to a 40% rise in their revenue growth [10].
 - Corporate Employees: We wish to get the attention and interest of the adult society, to bring in the adventure in their hectic routine lives. By incorporating the field trip ideas for companies and giving them a fun-filled experience, we wish to give the employees a great time out.

Market Strategies and Implementation

Strategy:1

We understand that accessibility to our Electric Race Cars needs to be to the most diverse sections of the society. With this aim in mind, we wish to provide the people of these sections with our Rent and Drive model. Using the tracks available to us; we create test drive events for Racing and EV enthusiasts where they can come to the track at their convenience and rent out the car to race [14].

Strategy:2

There are a lot of amateur and professional racers that hit the tracks on a regular basis. They tend to face high prices which poses as an obstacle to attend the Karting sessions. For the Racers who go to tracks regularly to improve their skills, we have planned for the Subscription model in which they can avail various benefits. This will not only provide us with the database for our marketing research through the Feedback forms and Social Media outlet responses, but also increase the trust and loyalty of our customer relations. This also enhances our Customer Satisfaction as we are able to cater to their demands as soon as possible [15].

Strategy:3

We have a desire to support the growing culture of the Karting and Racing in India. We want to build a social community that feels very passionate about driving. We want this community to be active and evergreen ergo we have special races planned for them. This will lead to increased interaction with each other and bring in a healthy competitive spirit among them. They will be able to track their performance and compare it with other racers and world-wide standings. This database will be present on our App along with tips and track advantages which will give an edge to them over the other drivers [15].

Strategy:4

Ojas World, being a very large step towards building our Brand Image is a one of a kind Entertainment and Leisure Hub for people to come and experience luxury with a flare of adrenaline. This idea is implemented to increase Brand Value and develop Brand Loyalty. The long-term goal for any organization, is to stay in the market as long as possible. With increased Brand Loyalty, Excellent Customer Satisfaction and High Brand-Value; we aim to achieve this long-term goal as an Entertainment and Recreation Hub in the market [17].

Strategy:5

Loyalty and Rewards program

The program would be to start off all our customers at the highest level of Rewards possible which would then grant them access to all the amenities and perks for a limited period of time. If a customer is not able to maintain a level of expenditure on our mall, then they are downgraded to the subsequent level. Key aspect of this loyalty program covers basic amenities such as priority parking for loyal customers of the mall, exclusive shopping days for members, VIP access to the mall lounge, access to Parents Lounges for parents to tend to their children or generally a place for the child to rest. Further to that, our loyalty program also features exclusive invites to events and celebrations [16].

Strategy:6

Flash Sale

We want to increase our footfall in Ojas World for which we have planned a Surprise Sale for a day where we would be giving various offers like a Buy one Get one or a 30% off on everything. Making it a regular increment in visitors, we would like to randomize the day every month and put out 5 days at the beginning of every month from which we choose; one of them to be the Surprise Sale Day. This plan would give an extra incentive for our customers [13]

Business Models: Commercialization of Electric Vehicles

1) Rent and Drive Model: The original concept of Arrive and Drive karting experience is one of the ways we can make karting accessible to the community. In this model, we would plan for people to come and instantly register to drive our Electric Formula Race Cars. We will be able to achieve this with our collaboration with race track owners spread across India [19].

2) Subscription Model: With the concept of Subscription to services booming in the recent years, we plan to have 2 subscription packages which our customers can avail to get various benefits. In the first plan, we will go for 15 free laps a month and a discounted price for every successive visit to our arrive and drive event. In the second plan, we have planned to give 25 laps a month, a discounted price along with merchandise and invites to special events [18].

3) Ojas World: Ojas World is a symbolical representation of what we as a team stand for. Ojas world depicts a perfect blend of our team's dual vision – Racing and Entertainment. With the operational controls of Ojas World in our hands, we will have flexibility, an increment in revenue with revenue diversification to facilitate a faster trajectory of growth for our organization. We plan to slowly develop brand loyalty and present our start-up as an Entertainment Hub. We would like to build our own brand image - to spread our Electric Racing Ideology. We plan on building a platform to show and experience the racing lifestyle. We plan to give the people an Entertainment Hub for leisure and recreation. We have planned a 2-floor infrastructure where we would like to incorporate the major Entertainment activities.

On the Ground Floor, we will have various Food Trucks and a Food court along with a Fine Dining Restaurant and Resto-Pub to give our guests an overall dining experience. These will provide a wide range of specialty dishes to our

customers. We would also provide an arcade gaming center for the enthusiastic people who love to enjoy and bring their inner child out to express it to everyone. Along with that, we have a Bowling Alley for a more relaxed experience with friends and family.

On the First Floor, we will have one-of-a-kind rooftop racetrack with a dynamic multi-level concept which will be an adrenaline rich racing experience. We have an exhibit to showcase the Development of Electric Vehicles through the years along with their induction in the motorsport field. The Continuous Process that the engineers have taken us through to develop a more sophisticated vehicle from our initial concept will be the highlight of the Exhibition.

4) B2C Model: This method of commercialization is the revenue generated from selling the vehicle directly to customers.

The cornerstone of this model is AIDA [11] which stands for Attention, Interest, Desire (or decision), Action and is the strategy which will make our customer interested and inquisitive about the car and then our product's distinguished feature will make want the car and jolt him into the action of buying the car. Various type of advertisements will generate attention to our brand, we will add consumer education elements in those advertisements to garner the interest of the consumers. With through education about the benefits of EV there will a tangible increase in interest. Once we have gathered information about the interested consumers, we will escalate our CRM through focused drip marketing through mail, messages, ads etc and hence push our sales force to convert the customers from desire to action.

We catch the attention of the customers using our varied and well thought marketing strategy. Social media plays a major role here. Our product is a unique product in an exciting field of racing. This will help in retaining the interest of the customers and make them desire the product. Our customer acquisition team will ensure that this desire motivates them to take the action of purchasing our car.

The advantages to the customer are:

- Ease of buying
- Ease of documentation
- Customizability
- 24/7 support
- Ojas app

Conclusion

The world is making efforts to reduce pollution and hence global warming. And along with this, the needs and desires of humans are rising day-by-day. The same will be applied to the racing and entertainment segments. Since the inception of electric go karts, this business model not only reduces the pollution generated by go karts running on conventional fuel but also the innovative marketing strategies which implemented all under one roof will make this industry more sustainable. Conclusively, by implementation of this business model the pollution reduces, an innovative way of generating revenue in a sustainable way is obtained and the same adrenaline gushing experience can be achieved.

References

1. <https://solarenergypanels.in/solar-power-plants/mw-solar-power-grid>
2. <http://www.businessenergy.com/electricity/>
3. <https://solarenergypanels.in/solar-power-plants/mw-solar-power-grid>
4. <https://auto.ndtv.com/news/bmw-believes-premium-car-sales-in-india-will-reach-1-lakh-units-by-2020-1257339>
5. <https://economictimes.indiatimes.com/markets/stocks/news/indias-switch-to-electric-vehicles-will-be-rapid-31m-evs-by-2040/articleshow/60403697.cms>
6. <http://news.bbc.co.uk/2/hi/business/8498507.stm>
7. http://www.espn.in/f1/story/_/id/21966301/f1-claims-fastest-growing-sport-brand-social-media
8. Ramachandra, T.V., Aithal, B.H. and Sreejith, K., 2015. GHG footprint of major cities in India. *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews*, 44, pp.473-495. (<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rser.2014.12.036>)
9. <https://www.atkearney.com/consumer-goods/article/?a/consumer-wealth-and-spending-the-12-trillion-opportunity>
10. <https://www.zuora.com/resource/subscription-economy-index/>
11. <https://www.smartinsights.com/traffic-building-strategy/offer-and-message-development/aida-model/>
12. <https://www.india-briefing.com/news/wp-content/uploads/2015/07/power-rates-by-state.jpg>
13. <https://economictimes.indiatimes.com/industry/services/retail/retailers-report-growth-in-sales-as-big-discounts-increase-footfall-at-shopping-malls/articleshow/67374888.cms?from=mdr>
14. <https://www.jaguar.in/news/taopt.html>
15. <https://www.redbull.com/in-en/red-bull-kart-fight-2018>
16. Jeevananda, S. (2018). *Influence of Customer Loyalty Programs on Buying Decisions Introduction*. November 2011.
17. <https://smaaash.in/mumbai/about>
18. <https://www.team-sport.co.uk/the-grid-go-karting-club/>
19. <https://smaaash.in/mumbai/attraction/sky-karting>